

So fierce, mom!

A study of LGBTQ+ colloquial language in Thailand in terms of
phonological and pragmatico-semantic changes

Natchanun Sanitdee

LDA-L312 Historical Linguistics

Linguistic Diversity and Digital Humanities Programme,

Faculty of Arts, University of Helsinki

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1. Introduction

The Global Digital Report 2019 found there are 51 million active internet social media users in Thailand, and it was ranked eighth in social media penetration, at 74% of the population (Leesa-Nguansuk 2019). Since the widespread use of the internet, Thai teenagers and young adults innovate countless colloquial vocabularies that have become viral in both online and real-life linguistic contexts. Thai society has demonstrated a high level of linguistic dynamic in terms of new words and meanings. Many of them originate from the LGBTQ+ community. It is interesting to examine these new words and meanings, as well as the factors contributing to the changes because they have a substantial effect on the development of modern Thai language.

This study aims to examine the changes of Thai words *มั่ง* /rɛːŋ/ meaning ‘strength’ and *แม่* /mɛː/ meaning ‘mother’ used colloquially under the frameworks of sound changes (Campbell 2013), semantic changes (Benjamin 2017), and causes of changes (Meillet 1905 & Ullmann 1963). The two words are chosen because they are among the top most common colloquial words that remain in use for a long period of time when compared with other less well-established colloquials or slangs that emerge and disappear more quickly. The results show that *มั่ง* /rɛːŋ/ ‘strength’ has a variety of colloquial usage depending on the contexts while *แม่* /mɛː/ ‘mother’ has less variations. In terms of phonological changes, *มั่ง* /rɛːŋ/ has gone through the processes of vowel lengthening, shortening, labialization, detriillization, and tonal shift. *แม่* /mɛː/ has variations of vowel lengthening and lowering. Regarding semantic changes, their meanings have been broadened, and *มั่ง* /rɛːŋ/ acquires a negative connotation (pejoration). The cause of changes is attributed to social causes as LGBTQ+ community invents the new usage of language to represent themselves as different and unique in the society, and members of the wider society adopt these innovations either as a sign of acceptance or simply because they are creative and sound fun to use. Thai culture also plays a crucial role because it guides the way Thai people interact with each other. In this case, different colloquial words and slangs especially those LGBTQ+-like make the interactions smooth and colorful.

1.1. Definitions and Theoretical Background

1.1.1. LGBTQ+

According to Oxford Learner's Dictionary, LGBTQ+ stands for lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and queer (or questioning). In this study, the focus group is ladyboys or shemales because they portray a colorful linguistic discourse. Ladyboys or shemales often create new words or new ways to use existing words, and they often become widely used in society. *มั่ง* /rɛːŋ/ and *แม่* /mɛː/ are also invented by ladyboys or shemales; therefore, the characteristics of variations mimic the speech manners of ladyboys or shemales, no matter in which group the language users are, whether inside of the LGBTQ+ community or other members in society.

1.1.2. Colloquial Language

มั่ง /rɛːŋ/ 'strength' and *แม่* /mɛː/ 'mother' in the sense created by ladyboys or shemales are considered colloquial language because they are used in an informal context which is in accordance with the definition Oxford Learner's Dictionary gives to the word 'colloquial' as '(of words and language) used in conversation but not in formal speech or writing'. The definition of 'colloquial' in this study is not only a temporary shift of utterance according to a certain context but a new usage of words in another sense or meaning.

Colloquial language is also used to represent a social group. James Clackson (2010) mentioned an experiment of a sociolinguist William Labov (1966) that shows that linguistic variation depends on a host of different factors other than the stylistic: age, sex, ethnicity, class, and speakers' self-perceptions can all interact with the variation between careful, formal, and casual speech. Labov's work clearly demonstrated that language may vary not only along a stylistic axis, from formal to informal, but also along other axes, relating to speakers' status and group membership (Clackson 2010: 10). LGBTQ+ community in Thailand use *มั่ง* /rɛːŋ/ and *แม่* /mɛː/ in their conversations as the representation of solidarity within the group.

1.1.3. Sound Changes

In the book *Historical Linguistics*, Campbell (2013: 28-39) lists Kinds of Common Sound Changes, namely deletions, epentheses or insertions, compensatory lengthening, and other 18 frequent sound changes, such as final-devoicing, nasal assimilation, palatalization, and deaffrication. Relevant sound changes found in this study are listed below.

1.1.3.1. Vowel lowering

Vowel lowering results in high vowels becoming mid or low vowels, or mid vowels becoming low. Low vowels are produced when the tongue is low because of the lowered mandible (Jakielski & Gildersleeve-Neumann 2016: 68).

1.1.3.2. Lengthening and Shortening

Lengthening refers to the change in which some sound, usually a vowel, is lengthened in some context. Shortening is the opposite in that the sound is shortened.

1.1.3.3. Others

Moreover, from the analysis, some other sound changes are found, i.e. labialization, tonal shift, and detrilization.

1.1.4. Semantic Changes

Benjamin (2017) categorizes semantic changes as follow:

1.1.4.1. Metaphoric Extension

A metaphor expresses a relationship between two things based on a perceived similarity between them. When a word undergoes metaphoric extension, it gets a new referent which has some characteristic in common with the old referent.

1.1.4.2. Metonymic Extension

Metonymic extension results in a word coming to have a new referent that is associated in some way with the original referent. The two referents here stand in a contiguity relationship with one another, rather than in a similarity relationship as with metaphoric change.

1.1.4.3. Broadening

A word that originally denoted one member of a particular set of things comes to denote more or all the members of that set.

1.1.4.4. Narrowing

Narrowing is the opposite of broadening – the restriction of a word’s semantic field, resulting in the word’s applying only to a subset of the referents that it used to be applied to.

1.1.4.5. Melioration and Pejoration

These are purely subjective terms referring to cases when a word’s meaning becomes either more positive (melioration or amelioration) or more negative (pejoration).

1.1.5. Causes of Changes

In his book, *The Principles of Semantics*, Ullmann (1963: 192) mentioned The Meillet theory’s (1905) three causes of changes and proposed the fourth factor as listed below.

1.1.5.1. Language-internal causes

Language-internal causes like grammaticalization or semantic change, semantic bleaching linked to grammatical change, for example.

1.1.5.2. Historical causes

Historical causes are a change in material culture/in the real world.

1.1.5.3. Social causes

Social causes mean when a word is used in a specialized group. Its meaning or sense can be more restricted or widened.

1.1.5.4. Psychological causes

Psychological causes cover forces like taboo, euphemism, synaesthesia, a spread of metaphors from frequently used areas, or avoidance of taboo words or obscene words.

1.2. Relevant Literature

There have been many linguistic studies conducted on LGBTQ+ colloquial words. Most of past studies are related to LGBTQ+ terminology (Panfil 2020, Vecchio 2021) and bullying discourses (Rivers & Duncan 2013). Kulick (2020) compared gay-and-lesbian-language studies between the 1980s and 1990s and concluded that scholars abandon the search for gay and lesbian language and move on to develop and refine concepts that permit the study of language and sexuality, and language and desire.

Some similar findings with this study are found in Vecchio's work (2021). Vecchio examined homosexual terminology like bisexual, trans, gay, and queer in different languages and found that in recent decades, LGBTQ become more self-assertive and demands for equality, and that queerness lexicon is highly dependent upon social factors and the communicative context.

This study puts an emphasis on ladyboys or shemales language variations in terms of phonological and pragmatico-semantic changes.

2. Data and Methods

In this study, two colloquial words are selected for the analysis:

(1) *ແຮງ*

/re:ŋ/

'strength'

(2) *ແມ່*

/mɛ:/

'mother'

These two words have been used among teenagers and young adults in Thailand for a long time when compared with other colloquial words or slangs that come and go rapidly. Their usage, especially the one of *๙๙๙* /rɛ:ŋ/ ‘strength’, is found in a very diverse contexts, and there are phonological and semantic changes that occur in each scenario.

The data will be analyzed based on the frameworks of Campbell (2013) in terms of sound changes, Benjamin (2017) in terms of semantic changes, and Meillet (1905) and Ullmann (1963) in terms of causes of changes.

3. Results

As there are multiple variations of *๙๙๙* /rɛ:ŋ/ ‘strength’ and *๙๙* /mɛ:/ ‘mother’ in different contexts, and some variations have both sound changes and semantic changes occurring at the same time, the analysis will be made based on an example with a situational context explained.

3.1. *๙๙๙* /rɛ:ŋ/ ‘strength’

3.1.1. Semantic Broadening and Pejoration

(Figure 1: A semantic map of the meaning of *๙๙๙* /rɛ:ŋ/)

Thai Dictionary, Royal Institute Edition 2011 provides definitions of *๒๓๖* /rɛːŋ/ as follow:

1. (n.) energy; run out of energy, a lot of energy or power, influence; human power, karma influence
2. (adj.) strong, bold; strong smell, bold personality
3. (adj.) with an enough energy or power
4. (adj.) sacred
5. (adj.) working rate of a person within a period of time
6. (v.) exert energy or power
7. (v.) focus energy on

๒๓๖ /rɛːŋ/ in this study is related to meaning 1, 2 and 3. The examples in section 3.1.2. below demonstrate that as the vowel becomes longer, the meaning of *๒๓๖* /rɛːŋ/ is broadened to convey the sense of being ‘fierce or confident’ and acquires a negative sense (pejoration) of being terrible.

3.1.2. Vowel Lengthening

- (3) *๒๓๖* *๓๓๓*
/rɛːŋ/ /maːk/
fierce.ADJ so.ADV
‘So fierce!’

The first and most prominent phonological characteristic of LGBTQ+ speech is vowel lengthening as ladyboys or shemales prefer their voice to sound feminine-like and smoother instead of short and harsh. The above example has vowel lengthening and is used to give a compliment on actions or ideas. For example, when a friend appeared at a party with stunning garments, another friend said...

- (4) *๒๓๖* *๒๓๖* *๒๓๖* *๓๓๓*
/tɛːhʉd/ /kɛː/ /rɛːŋ/ /maːk/
costume.NOM.SG your.POSS bold.ADJ so.ADV
‘Your costume looks so bold!’

Alternatively, it can be used to convey an opinion on an action or an idea in that it is too strong or fierce in the sense that it is terrible. In this case, the meaning of ᳚᳚᳚ /rɛ::ŋ/ becomes negative (pejoration). For instance, when a friend told a story of how their partner ended a relationship the previous night in an impolite way out of the blue, another friend said...

- (5) ᳚᳚᳚ ᳚᳚᳚
 /rɛ::ŋ/ /ma:k/
 terrible.ADJ so.ADV
 ‘(That was) so terrible!’

In addition, ᳚᳚᳚ /rɛ::ŋ/ can be used in a negative sentence used to prevent or tone down bold actions or ideas in an amicable, not a suppressive way. When a friend spoke too highly about him/herself that it became an exaggeration, another friend said...

- (6) ᳚᳚᳚ ᳚᳚᳚
 /ʔja:/ /rɛ::ŋ/
 don't.NEG confident.ADJ
 ‘Don't be (so) confident!’

With the presence of the word ᳚᳚ /ma:/ meaning ‘moving towards the speaker’, a speaker prevents the bold actions or ideas toward him/herself in an amicable way. For example, when a friend said s/he would reveal your embarrassing secret to other friends in the group, you said...

- (7) ᳚᳚᳚ ᳚᳚ ᳚᳚᳚
 /ʔja:/ /ma:/ /rɛ::ŋ/
 don't.NEG toward the speaker.LOC fierce.ADJ
 ‘Don't be (so) fierce with me!’ (LOC = locative)

Example 7 can also be used to convey a surprising feeling over some kind of offers, and ᳚᳚ /ma:/ in this sense will mean ‘become’; for example, when a friend offered to stay up all night to finish a project, you said...

- | | | |
|---|------------|------------|
| (8) <u>อย่า</u> | <u>มา</u> | <u>แรง</u> |
| /ɯjaː/ | /maː/ | /rɛːŋ/ |
| don't.NEG | become.PRS | fierce.ADJ |
| 'Don't be (so) fierce! (knowing that is unusual)' | | |

มา /maː/ in both contexts of *อย่ามาแรง* /ɯjaː maː rɛːŋ/ adds a sense of future actions.

Vowel lengthening is commonly found in other slangs or colloquial words originated from ladyboys or shemales as in the examples 9, 10, and 11.

- | | | |
|----------------|-----------------|---------------------|
| (9) <u>หนู</u> | (10) <u>ลูก</u> | (11) <u>ได้อยุ่</u> |
| /nuːː/ | /luːːk/ | /daiː ɯjuːː/ |
| 'rat' | 'child' | 'not bad' |

3.1.3. Labialization and Detrillization

- | | |
|--|-----------------|
| (12) <u>แรง</u> | (13) <u>แลง</u> |
| /r ^w ɛːŋ/ | /lɛːŋ/ |
| 'too intense' (w = labialization) | 'too intense' |

Labialization (example 12) and detrillization (example 13) occurs when *แรง* /rɛːŋ/ is used to comment or criticize a situation or a behavior that it is too intense, and the speakers want to dilute the concentration of the criticism and make it sound less formal. Both variations are used as a single word, and vowel lengthening is often found to accompany. They are usually spoken in a calm manner and low pitch of voice. An example situation would be when two friends were arguing, and one of them said something too strong, you said *แรง* /r^wɛːŋ/ or *แลง* /lɛːŋ/. Another example would be when your close colleague was criticized by a boss, and you witnessed the scene. After the boss left, you said *แรง* /r^wɛːŋ/ or *แลง* /lɛːŋ/ to your colleague to express sympathy and your opinion that what the boss did was too intense while keeping your opinion informal and light.

3.1.4. Tonal Shift and Vowel Shortening

- (14) มั่ง
 /r^wêŋ/
 ‘satisfyingly fierce’ (w = labialization)

มั่ง /r^wɛ:ŋ/ does not always have a negative connotation because it can also mean strong, bold, or fierce in a satisfying way. This variation contains a tonal shift and vowel shortening. มั่ง /r^wɛ:ŋ/ with a mid tone becomes มั่ง /r^wêŋ/ falling tone and a shorter vowel. It is usually used as a single word when, for example, you were watching a beauty contest, and the way a contestant walked on the stage was fierce and satisfying, you said มั่ง /r^wêŋ/ o give a compliment.

3.2. แม่ /mɛ:/ ‘mother’

3.2.1. Semantic Broadening

(Figure 2: A semantic map of the meaning of แม่ /mɛ:/)

According to Thai Dictionary, Royal Institute Edition 2011, แม่ /mɛ:/ ‘mother’ has 11 meanings as follow:

1. (n.) person who gives birth to a child
2. (n.) a term a senior woman uses to address a younger woman with intimacy or affinity
3. (n.) a female initial meaning a leader
4. (n.) a female who runs a business or has some profession
5. (n.) a female animal with a baby
6. (n.) a person who is a leader without indicating a gender
7. (n.) an appraising word for a goddess
8. (n.) a head of a group of similar stuff
9. (n.) a larger piece of the things used together
10. (n.) a river
11. (n.) a word or a syllable with a vowel but without a final consonant

แม่ /mɛ:/ ‘mother’ in the LGBTQ+ context has the closest meaning to meaning 3, 6, 7, and 8.

Due to a collective culture in Thailand, Thai people use family member vocabularies to address one another as an expression of a social bond. One can often hear a customer calling a seller aunt or uncle, or sometimes a service provider calls a customer brother or sister.

However, these family-related terms are rarely used to address friends. LGBTQ+ people, especially ladyboys or shemales, use แม่ /mɛ:/ to call their peers with a sense or admiration for being fierce or bold in personality. For example, when a friend was assertive with a taxi driver who pushed up a meter rate and used a wrong route to charge higher. The friend eloquently and successfully bargained the price down, you said...

(15)	<u>แม่</u>	<u>มาก</u>	<u>แม่</u>
	/rɛ:ŋ/	/ma:k/	/mɛ:/
	fierce.ADJ	so.ADV	mother.NOM.SG
	‘So fierce, mom!’		

ʌɪ /rɛ:ŋ/ has many variations depending on a different context as the original meaning as a noun shifts to adjective. Speakers often lengthen the vowel to express an admiration, a sympathy, a surprise, or to tone down bold actions. Alternatively, to make a criticism lighter, speakers will round their lips when pronouncing or de-thrill the /r/ consonant. The vowel can be shortened with a change of tone to express an excitement or give a compliment in a satisfying way.

On the other hand, ʌɪ /mɛ:/ ‘mother’ is used to address a ladyboy or shemale peer with a sense of admiration or leadership. The vowel is found to be lengthened and lowered when speakers want to convey a sense of superiority and intimacy.

Both words have changed due to a social cause because LGBTQ+ community wants to be unique, so they create their own sets of words. Then, as the colloquial words or the new meanings go viral, members outside of the community start to adopt the usage.

As this study is mainly based on observations as a Thai native speaker, it may be worth examining more LGBTQ+ colloquial words and variations, as well as the sources and means that allow them to spread. Moreover, taking the *Queens' English: The LGBTQIA+ Dictionary of Lingo and Colloquial Expressions* (Davis 2021) as a model, a Thai LGBTQ+ colloquial dictionary could be created.

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